

Design and Implementation of Solar Energy Monitoring System using LoRa for Solar Power Plants

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Abstract

The drastic decline in the fossil fuels paved the advent for renewable energy sources (RES) worldwide. Among the different available renewable energy sources, solar energy is widely used both domestically and commercially. Usually solar panels are placed over the rooftops or well away places from human movements, so it becomes difficult to monitor them. It is same with the case of wind energy generation, except for that it is not generated on rooftops. Moreover, it is possible to govern the power generating system more steadily. Therefore, it becomes essential to have a monitoring platform based on current, voltage and power measurement, which is proposed in this report using LoRa transmission. LoRa supports Long range of communication without the use of WiFi.

Keywords: *LoRa, Renewable Energy, Voltage sensor, Current Sensor, Node MCU, Semtech, Solar energy.*

1. Introduction

The most alarming environmental issue these days is the drastic declination in the fossil fuel levels. This turns on the need for the shift in energy production to renewable sources. Over the past few decades, the use of renewable sources has increased almost all over the world. This would be more economical if a few sophistications have been done to plants producing energy from renewable sources. This paper will put forward one such innovation of automating the production plant's efficiency monitoring system. Though it is available in plenty, renewable energy cannot be wasted, so there needs to be monitoring how much of energy is being taken out from the sources. Let us take an example of the hydro energy that is produced from water falling from great heights. There will be more amount of energy generated if the water is falling from great heights. So, in order to get the most energy out of the hydro production plant it is necessary to keep an eye over different parameters of energy that is produced. The parameters which have been taken here are the current, voltage, and power from the production of solar energy or basically, from a solar panel. Among all the available sources of renewable energy solar power is the one which is most easily available and also implementable. That is the reason why in this paper we are going to look into the monitoring of photo voltaic cell. This system of monitoring is done without any human involvement. Moreover, not even any involvement of error in monitoring. This helps in maintenance of the solar panel's durability, lifetime and efficiency.

2. Literature view

This paper will propose the implementation of a monitoring system for energy production from sunlight. The characteristic feature in this way of monitoring is the use of LoRa technology for transmission. This will be suitable for the renewable energy power plants as they will be located at places which are inaccessible for humans. The following literature presents a base for this report on

Renewable Energy monitoring using LoRa:

"A review of renewable energy sources, sustainability issues and climate change mitigation" by Phebe Asantewaa Owusu¹ and Samuel Asumadu-Sarkodie provides not only the different available renewable technologies but also the usage options of these various renewable sources. The climatic changes that are rapidly occurring in the recent times have been stated in this article. Thus, it gives the urgency to realize the importance of renewable energy sources [1]. The achievement of enduring development through renewable energy has been described in this article. A few hurdles affecting renewable energy sources have been defined. Organizing the energy transition from non-sustainable to renewable energy is often described as the major challenge of the first half of the twenty-first century [1]. In this article, a sensual data gives the proof of how a country's policy and policy instrument alter the cost and technological inventions.

"A smart energy distribution and management system for renewable energy distribution and context-aware services based on user patterns and load forecasting," by J. Byun, I. Hong, B. Kang and S. Park introduces the concept of smart energy distribution and management system (SEDMS) by giving the ill-effects of using a smart grid (generation part, transmission part, distribution part, and consumer part) systems [3].

2.1. IOT implementation using LoRa

Power efficient communication over long distances is enabled in recent times through the new transceiver technologies. LoRa is an example of such a LPWAN technology [2]. The establishment of communication between numerous devices in a large topology is the objective of this new transceiver system. An application of this may be the collection of meter readings in a city. In general, the use of powerful receiver will enhance the system such that the data is received in a single hop from simple devices. Then data from the receiver is sent over a wired infrastructure to a data collection point.

This is the general setup of an IOT system. Bearing this in mind, in this paper it is argued that LoRa is very useful to build more general IoT networks involving bi-directional multi-hop communications enabling sensing and propulsion. Over an inexpensive energy budget, the LoRa has the ability to transmit over large distances which would enable us to construct efficient IoT networks than currently possible. For example, mostly used ZigBee transceivers such as the Chipcon CC2420 cover a communication range of 20 m using 84.5 μ J (30-byte message) in a built-up environment [2]. Whereas, a LoRa Semtech SX1278 transceiver can cover a distance of 150 m using 86.5 mJ in the same environment. Besides improved communication range, the transceiver has unique features branching from the used modulation schemes. These specific capabilities of LoRa must be used when constructing a network to attain maximum performance in terms of communication and minimum in energy consumption. In this section we will see how LoRa technology will be used to build common IoT networks. The uncommon communication patterns of the LoRa Semtech SX1278 transceiver and the energy consumption patterns are analyzed. When building communication protocols using this technology such an analysis will be proven to be essential.

There are many more interesting features of LoRa in addition to the increased communication range which needs to be considered when building network protocols. Examples of such features are differentiation of channels by using different SF and carrier detection through CAD. To demonstrate the performance and capability of these features the available documentation is not enough. Hence, we have explained these features with a chain of experiments.

2.1.1. Spreading Factor: LoRa ranges over the spread factors from 7 to 12. Having SF12 as the longest time on air, SF7 being the shortest. The time on air will be doubled for every increment in spreading factor, which helps in transmitting the same amount of data. Less data is transmitted per unit time when longer time on air and a constant bandwidth are maintained. A 40dB packet is sent continuously with a fixed SF by the transmitter. The transmissions are received by the receiver on the same SF [2]. If a second transmitter is used it transmits continuously and sequentially with all other SF to the same receiver.

2.1.2. Concurrent Transmissions: For protocol design, concurrent transmissions of LoRa, which are nondestructive in nature, are considered valuable. Among the multiple different messages transmitted concurrently, depending on power levels and timing, one of the transmitted messages are received. Let us consider an experiment for understanding the in which exact conditions this effect is present in LoRa [2]. Consider a system having a receiver, a weak and a strong transmitter which differ by 1 dBm. With a definite header and CRC the two transmitters send one packet each. 16 32-byte packets were transmitted using first similar packet payloads and later a variety of payloads for each offset. Repeat the experiment with every combination of BW and SF. These results will be independent from either the transmission of different packet payload or the same one.

3. Block diagram and Description

The transmitting section working of a LoRa based renewable energy monitoring system is based on the block diagram below. The solar panel captures the energy from the sunlight through the photo voltaic cells and this in turn charges up the 12v battery. This voltage is used up by the DC motor which acts like a load. The amount of voltage and the amount of current are sensed by the voltage and current sensors. The current sensor used here is ACS712 [4]. Whereas the voltage sensor consists of the voltage divider circuit which senses the voltage [4]. The product of these values gives the power output. The LoRa module used here is Ra-02 transceiver. These sensed values are sent continuously to the Arduino NANO, which are transmitted to the receiver module in the form of packets.

Figure 1. Transmitter Block Diagram

Receiving section of the system is shown in the below block diagram. The transceiver LoRa module at the reception end of the system gets the data for every 5 seconds of interval. There are two microcontrollers used at the receiver end. The use of NodeMCU ESP8266 alone will not suffice the need for both the insertion of data in the database as well as interfacing with the LoRa transceiver. This is because the SPI protocol of ESP8266 is internally interfaced to the WiFi which makes its interfacing with the LoRa transceiver difficult. Therefore, an Arduino NANO is used to interface with the LoRa transceiver through SPI protocol. The received values are placed in the database when the NodeMCU is connected to the internet [4].

Figure 2. Receiver Block Diagram

3.1. Implemented system for solar energy monitoring

The below figures show the implemented system for solar energy monitoring using LoRa. Both the developed modules of transmitter and receiver seen below monitor the solar energy. The monitoring system of both the transmitter and the receiver side is done over a desktop/Laptop.

Figure 3. Transmitter Module

The desktop/Laptop used on the receiving side must have an internet connection to check the values uploaded over the database. Not only the database but also the serial monitor will display the received values without internet connection, but it doesn't store the received values.

Figure 4. Receiver Module

3.2. Design Flow Process

After the initialization of the sensors and the LoRa transceiver if the switch is turned ON then along with voltage values the current values are also sensed. If the switch is not turned ON then the controller waits for it to get turned ON. In the initialization part, the LoRa transceiver mainly establishes the channel with the other transceiver. The spreading factor, signal bandwidth parameters

of LoRa are set to 10 and 62.5MHz. Both the Lora transceivers are set to the same parameters, which enables the channel formation. Once both the current and voltage are received, they are multiplied with each other to obtain the power. These three values are sent in the form of packets by the LoRa transceiver.

Figure 5. Transmitter Process Flow

In the receiver part of the system there are no sensors to be initialized but only the LoRa transceiver. The initialization part of the transceiver involves setting the parameters of signal bandwidth and spreading factor. Later once the packet with the voltage current and power values are received, they are uploaded to the database. These database values can be compared time to time for any unstable values.

Figure 6. Receiver Process Flow

4. Results

The sensed voltage, current and power values at the transmitter side will be visible on the serial monitor. The screenshot of the values that are being transmitted over established LoRa channel are

visible below in figure7. In figure8, we can see the reception of the values of current, voltage and power in a database with respective date and time of reception.

Figure 7. Transmitter Side Serial Monitor

Sr.NO.	Voltage	Current	Power	Date&Time
1	12.23	0.05	0.61	2020-02-07 18:33:22
2	12.40	0.05	0.62	2020-02-07 18:33:39
3	12.50	0.06	0.69	2020-02-07 18:33:55
4		0.05	0.64	2020-02-07 18:34:15
5	12.38	0.05	0.58	2020-02-07 18:34:19
6	12.33	0.04	0.54	2020-02-07 18:34:24
7	12.28	0.07	0.91	2020-02-07 18:34:28
8	12.38	0.05	0.66	2020-02-07 18:34:33
9	12.35	0.06	0.73	2020-02-07 18:34:38
10	12.30	0.05	0.64	2020-02-07 18:34:44
11	12.33	0.06	0.68	2020-02-07 18:34:47
12	12.33	0.05	0.61	2020-02-07 18:34:52
13	12.35	0.05	0.64	2020-02-07 18:34:58
14	12.50	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:35:02
15	12.55	0.00		2020-02-07 18:35:27
16	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:38:12
17	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:38:18
18	12.60	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:38:22
19	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:14
20	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:18
21	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:23
22	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:29
23	12.55	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:34
24	12.57	0.00	0.00	2020-02-07 18:39:38

Figure 8. Result Received in the Database Server

5. Conclusion

There are a number of contemporary systems that exist to monitor the renewable energy. The principle aim was to create a similar system but with an improved technology. The use of LoRa most importantly will make the system power efficient. The added advantage of using LoRa is that it will

make the system accountable to large scale applications as well. The distance of the energy generation plant and the monitoring station is similar to that of the range provided by LoRa technology. Thus the use of LoRa in this application will make it useful to the greatest degree.

References

A review of renewable energy sources, sustainability issues and climate change mitigation, Phebe Asantewaa Owusu & Samuel Asumadu-Sarkodie, Cogent Engineering (2016), 3: 1167990.

- [1] https://eprints.lancs.ac.uk/id/eprint/77615/1/MadCom2016_LoRa_MAC.pdfgy
- [2] J. Byun, I. Hong, B. Kang and S. Park, "A smart energy distribution and management system for renewable energy distribution and context-aware services based on user patterns and load forecasting," in IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 436-444, May 2011.
- [3] J. Shah and B. Mishra, "IoT enabled environmental monitoring system for smart cities," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Internet Things Appl. (IOTA)*, Jan. 2016, pp. 383–388.

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